

Research

Finite Element Analysis Behavior of Concrete-Filled Double Skin Tubular Short Columns with External Stainless - Steel Tubes Under Axial Compression

Mohammad Rkibul Hassan^{1*}, Miao Zhai²

¹Department of Civil Engineering, Taiyuan University of Technology, Shanxi, Taiyuan, P.R China

²Department of Civil Engineering, Taiyuan University of Technology, Shanxi, Taiyuan, P.R China

***Corresponding author**

Accepted: 10 March, 2020; **Online:** 13 March, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3708532>

Abstract:

The increase use of the stainless steel in engineering, especially in some industrial architecture and ocean structure concrete filled double tubular column occurred which use stainless steel tube replaced the outer steel tube in CFDST. There has some research of CFDST on the static load, dynamic load, durability and construction loads, the study of CFDST with external stainless tube is still in its infancy. In this paper, using of “ABAQUS” establish finite element analysis model. In the analysis model, the all materials mechanic behavior and contact method have been defined. The comparison between the “ABAQUS” calculating results and the test results has showed their consistency. The proved model and orthogonal method, the parameter analysis has been carried out. To the stainless steel-concrete-steel tubular columns, the analysis parameters include nominal steel ratio, hollow ratio, concrete cube strength and the ratio of diameter of inner steel tube to thickness. Based on the parameter analysis, the calculating method for the ultimate bearing capacity of stainless - steel concrete which have been compared.

Keywords:

New type of Concrete Filled Double Skins Steel Tube, Parameter analysis calculating method.

1. Introduction

Concrete Filled Double Skins Steel Tube (CFDST) refers to a member formed by pouring concrete between a concentric outer steel pipe and an inner steel pipe. Compared with ordinary solid steel tube concrete, hollow laminated steel tube concrete inherits solid concrete filled steel tube. In addition to the advantages of better shape and toughness, convenient construction, etc., it also has a series of new advantages. According to the performance, the hollow sandwich steel tube concrete replaces part of the core concrete by hollow steel pipe, which can greatly reduce the amount of

concrete and reduce the structural weight. Not only reduces the project cost, but also facilitates engineering installation. At the same time, the solid bearing capacity of the same section is not significantly reduced, and the overall cost performance is very high. Concrete exists between the inner and outer steel pipes. When a fire occurs, the concrete has a certain heat insulation effect. Therefore, the strength of the inner steel pipe is not significantly reduced, and the support can be effectively provided to prevent rapid structural damage during fire, and the structure can be effectively improved performance. The hollow-sandwich steel tube concrete is hollow, and the overall rigidity is small compared with the solid steel tube concrete. When the earthquake occurs, the hollow sandwich steel tube concrete as the supporting structure bears less horizontal seismic force and can greatly improve the seismic performance of the building. Stainless Steel is a metal that has high chemical stability in water, air, acid-base salt solutions and other corrosive media, and maintains its excellent physical and mechanical properties at high temperatures. Stainless steel is not wear-resistant but corrosion-resistant. Its main constituent elements are C (carbon), Cr (chromium), Ni, Ti, Mn. Stainless steel has many irreplaceable characteristics, mainly as follows:

Good corrosion resistance

The principle is that stainless steel contains a lot of Cr (chromium), while Cr is easier to interact with in the air. Oxygen reacts and forms an oxide film on the surface of the metal that isolates the corrosive material from the metal surface to the outside. Therefore, stainless steel has excellent chemical and corrosion resistance and electrochemical corrosion resistance. The higher the chromium content of stainless steel, the stronger the corrosion resistance, and the higher the carbon content, the worse the corrosion resistance. Therefore, the Cr (chromium) content of stainless steel with excellent performance is greater than 10.5%, and the carbon content should not exceed 1.2%.

High strength, good plasticity and toughness

It can be seen from the typical stainless - steel stress-strain curve that it exhibits significant stress enhancement when the stainless steel undergoes large strain. In addition, the cross-sectional elongation of stainless steel is about twice that of ordinary steel.

High temperature resistance

Stainless steel can maintain its good physical and mechanical properties at high temperatures. It is a widely used heat-resistant material.

Surface cleaning beautiful

Stainless steel products can be treated with a polishing technique to give the metal surface a mirror-gloss, with a good decorative effect and simple maintenance.

Good process performance

Due to the high plasticity of stainless steel, it can be processed into stainless steel products of various shapes. In view of this, stainless steel has been used in many important projects.

Nomenclature

A_c	Cross-sectional area of concrete
A_{ce}	Internal void area included in the outer steel tube section
A_{so}	Cross section area of outer steel tube
A_{si}	Inner steel tube cross-sectional area
D_o	Outer steel tube diameter
D_i	Inner diameter of steel pip
t_o	Thickness of outer steel pipe
t_i	Inner steel pipe thickness
E_o	Initial elastic modulus of the material
E_c	Concrete elastic modulus
E_s	Steel modulus of elasticity
$f'c$	Concrete cylinder compressive strength
f_{ck}	Concrete axial compressive strength
f_{cu}	Concrete cube compressive strength
f_t	Concrete axial tensile strength
f_{yo}	Yield strength of outer steel tube
f_{yi}	Yield strength of inner steel tube steel
f_{scy}	Overall compressive yield strength of outer steel tube and concrete
α	Member section steel content ($\alpha = A_{so}/A_c$)
α_n	Nominal steel content of the component ($\alpha = A_{so}/A_{ce}$)
L	Test piece length
x	Hollow ratio
N_u	Column ultimate carrying capacity wind
ε	Strain

μ_c	Concrete Poisson's ratio
μ_s	Steel Poisson's ratio
Nosc, u	Ultimate bearing capacity of concrete and outer steel tubes
A_{sc}	Cross section area of outer steel tube
ξ	Concrete filled steel tube restraint effect coefficient ($\xi = A_s f_y / A_c f_{ck}$)
ρ_c	Concrete density
ρ_s	Steel density
σ	stress
f_{cc}	Compressive strength
f_s	Axial compressive strength of inner steel pipe of test piece
A_c	Normal cross-sectional area of test piece concrete
A_s	The cross-sectional area of the inner steel pipe of the test piece
f_i	Lateral binding force
f_{co}	Concrete compressive strength
N_s	The product of the standard value of the inner steel tube and its interface area

2. Finite Element Model

2.1 Material Constitutive

1. Stainless steel: The Ramberg-Osgood model proposed by Ramberg and Osgood^[31] is a theoretical model for describing the stress-strain curve of elastoplastic materials in solid mechanics. In this model, the total strain is the sum of the elastic strain and the plastic strain.

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon_e + \varepsilon_p = \frac{\sigma}{E_0} + 0.002 \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{0.2}} \right)^n$$

Where, E_0 is initial elastic modulus of the material; n is the strain hardening index, which is a parameter reflecting the nonlinearity of the stress-strain curve of the material, $\sigma_{0.2}$ is the corresponding stress when the material residual strain is 0.2%.

According to a large number of experimental studies, Ramberg-Osgood the strain value of the material $\varepsilon_{0.2}$, sufficiently describe the stress and strain curve of the material; But when the strain value of the material is greater than $\varepsilon_{0.2}$, in the stress-strain curve described by this model, the stress value of the material is higher than the test value.

Macdonald^[32] et al. Believe that the material strain hardening index in the Ramberg-Osgood model is only related to the small stress value $\sigma_{0.2}$ and $\sigma_{0.01}$ related, it is not suitable for large strain situations, so the following constitutive equation is proposed:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\sigma}{E_0} + 0.002 \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{1.0}} \right)^{[i+j\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{1.0}}\right)^k]}$$

Where, $\sigma_{1.0}$ The stress of the material when the total strain is 1%; i, j, k is a parameter that changes significantly with the thickness and type of the material, and cannot be calculated using a unified formula, and can only be obtained by corresponding tests. Therefore, the usability of this constitutive relationship is greatly restricted.

Olsson^[33] 11 After a large number of tests, when the total strain of the stainless steel material is greater than 2%, The real stress and engineering strain have a linear relationship, so the Olsson model is: when the total material strain is less than 2%, the Ramberg-Osgood model is used; when the total material strain is greater than 2% N, the stress described by the Ramberg-Osgood model is The curve is transformed into the real stress-engineering strain relationship curve of the material in $(\varepsilon_{2.0}, \sigma_{2.0})$ Lines are drawn at points to describe the stress-strain relationship of stainless steel materials. Because the model is based on the Ramberg-Osgood model when the total strain is less than 2%, Therefore, when the strain of the material is changed within the range of $\varepsilon_{0.2} \sim \varepsilon_{2.0}$, the stress-strain relationship of the material cannot be accurately described.

Mirambell^[34] and Real and experiment, based on the traditional Ramberg-Osgood model, the constitutive equation of stainless steel is proposed:

$$\varepsilon = \begin{cases} \frac{\sigma}{E_0} + 0.002 \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{0.2}} \right)^n, & \sigma < \sigma_{0.2} \\ \frac{\sigma - \sigma_{0.2}}{E_{0.2}} + \varepsilon_{\rho u} \left(\frac{\sigma - \sigma_{0.2}}{\sigma_u - \sigma_{0.2}} \right)^{n'_{0.2,u}} + \varepsilon_{0.2}, & \sigma \geq \sigma_{0.2} \end{cases}$$

where, $E_{0.2}$ the corresponding stress when the stress is equal to $\sigma_{0.2}$, $\varepsilon_{\rho u}$ and σ_u Respectively the ultimate forming strain and the ultimate stress; $n'_{0.2,u}$ and $\sigma_u, \sigma_{0.2}$ Strain hardening index of the curve segment. In this model, the ultimate forming strain and ultimate stress of the material are not easy to obtain, and the stress-strain relationship of the material cannot be accurately reflected when the stainless steel is compressed.

Rasmussen^[35] also proposed the constitutive equation of stainless steel based on the traditional Ramberg-Osgood model:

$$\varepsilon = \begin{cases} \frac{\sigma}{E_0} + 0.002 \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{0.2}} \right)^n, & \sigma < \sigma_{0.2} \\ \frac{\sigma - \sigma_{0.2}}{E_{0.2}} + \varepsilon_u \left(\frac{\sigma - \sigma_{0.2}}{\sigma_u - \sigma_{0.2}} \right)^m + \varepsilon_{0.2}, & \sigma \geq \sigma_{0.2} \end{cases}$$

Where, $\varepsilon_{0.2} = \frac{\sigma_{0.2}}{E_0} + 0.002$, $E_{0.2} = \frac{E_0}{1+0.002n/e}$, $e = \frac{\sigma_{0.2}}{E_0}$, $m = 1 + 3.5 \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_u} \right)$,

$$\varepsilon_u = 1 - \frac{\sigma_{0.2}}{E_0}, \sigma_u = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{0.2 + 185e} \cdot \sigma_{0.2}, & \text{Austenitic stainless steel, duplex stainless steel} \\ \frac{1 - 0.0375(n - 5)}{0.2 + 185e} \cdot \sigma_{0.2}, & \text{Ferritic stainless steel} \end{cases}$$

2.Steel: The inner steel pipe of the test piece is Q235 carbon steel, which belongs to low carbon soft steel. Based on a large number of previous tensile tests, this paper uses the stress-strain relationship shown in Figure 2-1, including the elastic phase, elastoplastic phase, plastic phase, and secondary plastic flow phase. Five sections are used in the static load test. Constitutive relationship of steel. It is similar to the stress-strain relationship during unidirectional stretching. For the convenience of calculation, the strengthening section is taken as a linear relationship material. After the material enters the failure surface, a horizontal plastic section is used.

Fig 2-1: constitutive model of steel

At present, there are two most used models. One is the Cowper-Symonds model, which is used to calculate the problem of lower strain rate, and the other is the Johnson-C1ook model, which is suitable for the problem of higher strain rate.

The strain rate of the new hollow sandwich concrete composite structure studied in this paper is relatively low, so the Cowper-Symonds model is used in the calculation. The model is shown in

equation, where the strain rate of the steel is superimposed, σ_d Is the stress value of the steel when the strain rate is overlapped, σ_s It is the stress value of the steel under static force. D and p material strain rate coefficients.

$$\sigma_d/\sigma_s = 1 + (\varepsilon/D)^{1/p}$$

The parameters D and P in the model can be obtained by fitting property tests. In the absence of relevant test data, empirical values may be used. Among them, for low carbon steel, Numerous tests have shown that when $D = 40.4s^{-1}$, $p = 5$. The time model can well reflect the increase in the ultimate strength of the steel. As mentioned earlier, with the development of strain strengthening, the strain rate effect of steel is reduced, and the calculation of the ultimate strength of steel is usually taken as $D = 6844s^{-1}$, $p = 3.91$.

Abramowicz and Jones, 1984, 1986; Reid and Reddy, 1986; Reid et al., 1986. In this paper, when the simulation of H-shaped steel specimens under impact load is performed, the strain at the impact point of the steel is often large $D = 6844s^{-1}$, $p = 3.91$ calculate its strain rate effect.

3. Concrete: In concrete-filled steel tube, the stress-strain relationship model of the core concrete in the compression zone is determined by the concrete itself and the outer steel tube. The influence of the outer steel tube on the concrete stress-strain relationship model can be described by the constraint effect coefficient f. When the value of f is larger, the decline section of the stress-strain relationship curve of the core concrete appears later, and the downward trend is most gentle: when the specific value is smaller, the decline section of the stress-strain relationship curve of the core concrete appears earlier. And the steeper the downward trend. The longitudinal stress-strain relationship of the core concrete in concrete-filled steel tube proposed for concrete in the compression zone is as follows:

$$y = 2x - x^2 \quad (x \leq 1)$$

$$y = \begin{cases} 1 + q \cdot (x^{0.1\xi} - 1) & (\xi \geq 1.12) \\ \frac{x}{\beta \cdot (x - 1)^2 + x} & (\xi < 1.2) \end{cases} \quad (x > 1)$$

where, $x = \frac{\varepsilon}{\varepsilon_0}$, $y = \frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0}$, $\sigma_0 = \left[1 + (-0.054 \cdot \xi^2 + 0.4 \cdot \xi) \cdot \left(\frac{24}{f'_c}\right)^{0.45} \right] \cdot f'_c$,

$$\varepsilon_0 = \varepsilon_{cc} + \left[1400 + 800 \cdot \left(\frac{f'_c}{24} - 1 \right) \right] \cdot \xi^{0.2} (\mu\varepsilon), \quad \varepsilon_{cc} = 1300 + 12.5 \cdot f'_c (\mu\varepsilon),$$

$q = \frac{\xi^{0.745}}{2+\xi}$, $\beta = (2.36 \times 10^{-5})^{[0.25+(\xi-0.5)^7]} \cdot f'_c \cdot 3.51 \times 10^{-4} \cdot f'_c$ Axial resistance of concrete cylinder compressive strength.

The stress-strain relationship of concrete in the tension zone in this paper adopts the model proposed in:

$$y = \begin{cases} 1.2x - 0.2x^6 & (x \leq 1) \\ \frac{x}{0.031} \sigma_p^2 (x - 1)^{1.7} + x & (x > 1) \end{cases}$$

Where, $x = \frac{\varepsilon_c}{\varepsilon_p}$, $y = \frac{\sigma_c}{\sigma_p}$; $\sigma_p = 0.26(1.25f'_c)^{2/3}$, $\varepsilon_p = 43.1\sigma_p(\mu\varepsilon)$

In addition to considering stress and strain, the relevant density must be defined for the model. The density of steel is 7850kg / m³ and the density of concrete is 2500kg / m³.

2.2 Finite Element Analysis

The size of the grid division is closely related to the calculation accuracy. To obtain high-precision calculation results, the grid division often needs to be dense. The denseness of the grid division will greatly affect the calculation speed of the finite element software. In order to obtain the highest performance price Compared with adjusting the size of the grid under reasonable calculation accuracy, better data can be obtained in a shorter time. The test unit in this paper is divided as follows, where the grid length of the test piece in the axial direction is 0.01m and the ring direction is every 150 grids, as shown in Figure 2-2.

Fig 2-2: Mesh map of Specimen

In the analysis, we call the problem of the linear relationship between the external load and the response of the research system as a linear analysis problem. In the real physical structure, the stiffness of the structure or component will change with deformation, which is called the nonlinear problem. Nonlinear problems can be generally divided into the following three categories: geometric nonlinearity, boundary condition nonlinearity, and material nonlinearity. Boundary condition nonlinearity means that the boundary conditions will change during the entire stress analysis. In this paper, the normal contact behavior between the inner and outer steel tubes and concrete is defined as hard contact. The size of the contact pressure is not limited. If the pressure on the contact surface becomes zero or negative, it means that the two contact surfaces have separated; the non-linearity of the material refers to the non-linearity of the material stress. The problem of deformation will have the problem of material nonlinearity; geometric nonlinearity means that when the component undergoes large deformation, the relationship between load and displacement does not obey the linear relationship. In summary, the axial compression simulation analysis of the new type of hollow sandwich concrete composite members includes three types of nonlinear problems: material, geometry, and boundary conditions. The finite element analysis in this paper uses the complete Newton method to solve iteratively.

2.3 Finite Element Model Verification

The contents of finite element verification include comparison verification of failure mode and comparison verification of load and displacement curve.

1. Comparison of failure modes of stainless - steel pipe, concrete and steel pipe composite short columns.

(1) Comparison of failure modes of HSCSC48 stainless steel pipe, concrete and steel pipe composite short columns.

Fig 2-3: Failure Modes contrast of HSCSC48 specimen

From the Fig 2-3 it can be seen that the part with the highest stress in the simulation result is the middle part of the test piece, which appears as a middle protrusion. The first raised part of the test piece is the upper end of the test piece, and then the middle is raised; while the first raised part of the HSCSC48-c test piece is the middle part of the test piece, and then the upper and lower parts of the test piece are close to the end plate. There were multiple bumps again, and the failure shape of the test piece was similar to the simulation result, indicating that the end plate would affect the failure shape of the test piece. The first bump occurred generally at the end of the test piece without the end plate. If there are end plates at both ends, the first raised part is the middle part of the test piece.

(2) Comparison of failure modes of 76mm inner diameter stainless steel tube-concrete steel tube composite short columns.

Fig 2-4: Failure Modes contrast of HSCSC76 specimen

From the Fig 2-4 it can be seen that the part with the highest stress in the simulation result is the middle part of the test piece, which is shown as a middle protrusion. The first raised part of the HSCSC76-b test piece is the upper end of the test piece, and then multiple protrusions also appeared in the upper and lower parts of the test piece. In the middle part of the test piece, multiple protrusions appeared in the upper and lower parts of the test piece later. The failure shape of the test piece is similar to the simulation result, indicating that the end plate will affect the failure shape of the test piece. The starting part is generally the end of the test piece without an end plate. If there are end plates at both ends, the first raised part is the middle of the test piece.

(3) Comparison of failure modes of 89mm inner diameter stainless steel pipe-concrete-steel pipe short columns.

Fig 2-5: Failure Modes contrast of HSCSC89 specimen

From the Fig 2-5 it can be seen that the part with the highest stress in the simulation result is the middle part of the test piece, which appears as a convex part in the middle. The first part of HSCSC89-a specimen to be raised is the upper end, and then a middle raised. The condition of the HSCSC89-b test piece is similar to that of the HSCSC89-a, while the first raised part of the HSCSC89-c test piece is the lower part of the test piece, and then multiple protrusions appear in the upper and lower parts of the test piece. The failure shape of the piece is similar to the simulation result, which indicates that the end plate will affect the failure shape of the test piece. The first place where the protrusion occurs is generally the end of the test piece without the end plate. If both ends have end plates, the most. The first raised part is the middle part of the test piece.

2. Comparison of failure curve of stainless - steel tube concrete steel tube composite short column.

Fig 2-6: Load-displacement curve of 48mm, 76mm, 89mm

From the above load-displacement curve, it can be seen that the simulated load of the test specimen is not much different from the ultimate load of the test result, but the displacement of the ultimate load point occurs. The test result is slightly larger than the simulated result. After analysis, the reason is that the concrete is poured into the test specimen. Due to the shrinkage during the setting and hardening of the concrete, the concrete between the two layers of steel tubes is slightly dense, which is manifested as a little gap between the uppermost concrete of the specimen and the upper end plate. Therefore, the concrete did not directly bear the load at the beginning of loading, only two steel pipe bears the load, and the concrete begins to bear the load directly after the displacement reaches a certain value.

3. Parametric Study

For the test of one or two factors, because there are fewer factors, the implementation of the test and the analysis of parameters are relatively simple. In real life, it is often necessary to study and consider 3 or more test factors. Quite large and difficult to implement (Orthogonal experimental design) is an effective and convenient method for studying multi-factor and multi-level experiments. It is based on the principle of orthogonality, selects some representative points from a comprehensive experiment, and makes reasonable combinations to make each factor Each level of one factor meets once per level, and this is what is called orthogonality. The orthogonal table is based on the principle of orthogonality to select the horizontal combinations of orthogonal

experiments and list them into a table. For example, a three-factor three-level test, if a comprehensive test is conducted, 27 groups of experiments must be arranged. Such as: If the test is performed according to the $L_9(3)$ submission form, it only needs to be done 9 times. If the submission is performed according to $L_{18}(3)$ t, only 18 experiments are required. The orthogonal test can greatly reduce the workload. Therefore, orthogonal experimental design is widely used in many field domains. There are many parameters that can be studied for the new hollow sandwich concrete composite structure, including hollow ratio, nominal the steel content, the ratio of the inner pipe diameter to the thickness, the outer pipe strength, the inner pipe strength, etc., if they are combined one by one, many combinations are produced, which is the so-called comprehensive test. If one-by-one calculations are performed using finite element software, it takes too long, so this article uses the orthogonal test method to deal with this problem. The orthogonal test method can effectively select a typical combination example is developed for analysis, which greatly saves finite element calculations and improves efficiency. A cross - tab is a set of regular design tables. It is mainly composed of experimental factors and levels. Its representation method is $L_9(3^4)$, where "L" is the meaning of an orthogonal table; the number "9" means 9 rows, that is the orthogonal table can arrange 9 combinations of experiments; the base number "3" in parentheses represents the number of levels of each factor, and the index "4" of 3 in parentheses represents 4 columns. A maximum of 4 can be performed with this orthogonal table 3 level factor test.

3.1 Parameter analysis of Stainless - steel tube-concrete-steel tube composite short column

3.1.1 Parameter analysis conditions

Corrugated steel pipe-concrete steel pipe combined short column axial compression test is designed with 4 factors and 3 horizontal orthogonal tables. The factors are hollow ratio, concrete strength, nominal steel content ratio, and inner tube diameter-thickness ratio. The value ranges of the factors are hollow. Rate (0.4-0.8m), concrete strength (C30-C70), nominal steel content (0.05-0.11), inner tube diameter-thickness ratio (20.60). Table 4-1 is an orthogonal table for the design of stainless - steel pipe-concrete-steel pipe short columns.

Table 3-1: Orthogonal

Factor	Hollow ratio (χ)	Concrete strength (Mpa)	Nominal steel content	Inner diameter thickness ratio
1	0.4	C30	0.05	20
2	0.4	C50	0.08	40
3	0.4	C70	0.11	60
4	0.6	C30	0.08	60
5	0.6	C50	0.11	20
6	0.6	C70	0.05	40
7	0.8	C30	0.11	40
8	0.8	C50	0.05	60
9	0.8	C70	0.08	20

The following figure 3-1 is the corresponding load-displacement diagram for each group in the orthogonal table. From the figure, the corresponding load and displacement relationship of each group of tests can be obtained.

Fig 3-1: Load - displacement curve of each factor

As shown in Figure 3-1 above, the load and displacement curves recorded by the axial compression simulation of the test specimens for each factor. At the beginning of loading, both the load and the displacement have a linear relationship with the progress of the load. When the load reaches the

limit load, the specimen gradually yields. The load begins to decrease with the increase of the displacement. Post-load capacity.

3.1.2 Parameter analysis results

There are generally two methods for the design and analysis of orthogonal experiments: one is called range analysis and the other is called analysis of variance. The range analysis method is used in this paper. It is simple, convenient, popular, and easy to understand. It is widely used in actual life.

The range analysis method is referred to as the R method. It first needs to perform calculations, and judge each factor based on the calculations.

In the test K_{jm} is the sum of the index corresponding to the m level of factor j, and $\overline{K_{jm}}$ is the average value of K_{jm} . By K_{jm} can determine the degree of influence of factor j on the test. R_j is the extreme difference of the j factor, that is, the difference between the maximum value and the minimum value of the factor in the j column:

$$R_j = \max(\overline{K_{jm}}) - \min(\overline{K_{jm}})$$

When each level of the j factor reflected by R_j changes within a given range, the magnitude of the change in the corresponding test index. The larger R_j the greater its impact on the test index, and the more important it is. Therefore, according to the size of R_j , the order of the influence of each factor on the test index can be obtained. The calculation and judgment of the range analysis method can be performed directly on the test result analysis table. As shown in Table 3-2:

Table 3-2: Analysis of test results

Factor	A Hollow Ratio x	B Concrete strength (Mpa)	C Nominal steel content a_n	D Inner diameter thickness ratio (Mpa)	Y Ultimate load (KN)
1	0.4	C30	0.05	20	494 KN
2	0.4	C50	0.08	40	685 KN
3	0.4	C70	0.11	60	668 KN
4	0.6	C30	0.08	60	490 KN
5	0.6	C50	0.11	20	864 KN
6	0.6	C70	0.05	40	652 KN
7	0.8	C30	0.11	40	636 KN
8	0.8	C50	0.05	60	430 KN
9	0.8	C70	0.08	20	791 KN
K_1	2148	1620	1576	2149	
K_2	2007	1979	1966	1973	
K_3	1857	2411	2468	1888	
$\overline{K_1}$	716	540	525	716	
$\overline{K_2}$	669	660	655	658	
$\overline{K_3}$	619	804	823	629	
R_j	97	264	298	87	

The level A of the first column of the factor A (hollow ratio), the corresponding test index and the average calculation method are:

$$K_{A1} = y_1 + y_2 + y_3 = 494 + 685 + 968 = 2148$$

$$\overline{K_{A1}} = \frac{K_{A1}}{3} = 716$$

The second level A of factor A. And 3rd level A. Calculation method and A. Same as:

$$K_{A2} = y_4 + y_5 + y_6 = 490 + 864 + 652 = 2007$$

$$\overline{K_{A2}} = \frac{K_{A2}}{3} = 669$$

$$K_{A3} = y_7 + y_8 + y_9 = 636 + 430 + 791 = 1857$$

$$\overline{K_{A3}} = \frac{K_{A3}}{3} = 619$$

Determine the major and minor order of factors, Range R, calculated by definition, such as:

$$R_A = \overline{K_{A1}} - \overline{K_{A3}} = 716 - 619 = 97$$

Similarly, can be found R_B, R_C and R_D . The calculation results are listed in the table above.

3.1.3 Whole process analysis

This article analyzes the load-displacement curve of the test members. Figure 3-2 shows the typical stress-strain relationship curve of a stainless - steel tube-concrete-steel tube composite short column. The shape of the stress-strain relationship curve of stainless - steel pipe-concrete-steel pipe short columns is closely related to the constraint effect *coefficient*^[531]. When $\xi < \xi_o$. When the curve reaches the extreme point, it enters the descending section. The smaller ξ decline; when the $\xi \geq \xi_o$. At this time, the descending section of the curve is not very obvious, and it increases slightly with the increasing amplitude of the curve ξ_o . The value is related to the cross-sectional shape of the hollow sandwich concrete-filled steel tube. For circular hollow sandwich concrete-filled steel tube, wool is generally taken $\xi_o \approx 1$. Four characteristic points are selected in the curve shown in Figure 4-3 respectively: point A is the point at which the stainless - steel outer tube begins to enter the elastoplastic phase; point B is the point at which the stainless - steel tube begins to enter the yield phase; point C has reached the ultimate bearing capacity; point D The longitudinal strain of stainless - steel outer steel tube reaches 20,000 micro strain.

Stress-strain curve

Fig 3-2: Load - displacement curve of HSCSC

- (1) Elastic stage (OA): Concrete, inner steel pipe, and outer stainless - steel pipe generally subjected to separate forces. At point A, the outer stainless - steel pipe enters the elasto - plastic stage, and then the inner steel pipe also begins to enter the elasto - plastic stage. The stress distribution is uniform.
- (2) Elastic-plastic phase (AB): The longitudinal stress of concrete begins to increase significantly, f_c reaching the compressive strength of the cylinder at point B. The lateral deformation coefficient of concrete exceeds the lateral deformation coefficient of the outer stainless - steel pipe, so the interaction between the two begin. The outer steel pipe first yields and enters the plastic stage; after that, the inner steel pipe also yields.
- (3) Sexual Stage (BC): The longitudinal stress of the concrete continues to increase. At point C, the overall bearing capacity of the concrete and the inner and outer steel pipes reaches its limit. At this moment, the longitudinal stress of the concrete has exceeded its compressive strength of the cylinder f_c , which fully shows that the restraint effect of the outer steel tube makes the strength of the concrete in the core area greatly improved.
- (4) Falling Segment (CD): After point C, that is, after the peak, the longitudinal stress of the specimen began to decrease.

3.2 Quantitative parameter analysis

Quantitative analysis is mainly performed on parameters such as nominal steel content ratio, hollow ratio, degree of coagulation strength, and diameter-to-thickness ratio of the stainless - steel pipe-concrete-steel pipe short column.

3.2.1 Effect of nominal steel content

The variation range of the nominal steel content of the test specimen in this paper is 0.05n0.1 l. The nominal steel content of the corresponding test specimen is adjusted by adjusting the thickness of the outer steel pipe. Shown are the load and displacement curves of the specimens with nominal steel content ratios of 0.05, 0.10, and 0.15. When the nominal steel content ratio is 0.05, 0.10, 0.15, the corresponding ultimate bearing capacity of the component is 509KN, 646KN, 785KN. When the nominal steel content ratio is increased from 0.05 to 0.15, the ultimate bearing capacity of the component increases. The range reached 54%. It can be seen that increasing the nominal steel content of the component can greatly increase the ultimate bearing capacity of the specimen, mainly because the constraint effect coefficient of the component and the nominal the steel ratio

has a linear relationship. The larger the nominal steel content, the greater the constraint effect coefficient, and the larger the constraint effect coefficient, the greater the external stainless - steel pipe's constraint force on the concrete in the core area, and the greater the ultimate bearing capacity of the component.

Fig 3-3: The effect of different Nominal steel ratio

3.2.2 Effect of concrete strength

The strength of the concrete studied in this paper ranges from C30 to C70. When finite element analysis is performed, only the strength of the component concrete is changed, and the influence of a single factor on the axial compression performance of the specimen is analyzed. The figure shows the load-displacement curve when the concrete strength is C30, C50, C70. As can be seen from the figure, the component has a mid-span load under three different concrete strengths. The displacement curve slightly increases: the ultimate bearing capacity of the components corresponding to C30, C50, and C70 concrete are 454KN, 567KN, and 640KN, respectively. When the concrete strength increases from C30 to At C70, the ultimate bearing capacity of the component increased by 40%. Therefore, it shows that the strength of concrete can greatly increase the ultimate bearing capacity of axial compression test pieces.

Fig 3-4: The effect of different concrete strength

3.2.3 Effect of Hollow Ratio

In order to study the influence of the hollow ratio on the axial compressive performance of the component, the hollow ratio of the test piece is selected from 0.4 to 0.8. The figure shows the component load-displacement curves corresponding to hollow ratios of 0.4, 0.6, and 0.8. It can be seen from the figure that the load-displacement curve decreases as the hollow ratio of the specimen increases. The ultimate bearing capacity of components with hollow ratios of 0.4, 0.6, and 0.8 are 749KN, 700KN, and 589KN, respectively. When the hollow ratio increases from 0.4 to 0.8, the ultimate bearing capacity of the test piece decreases by 21%. In the parameter analysis, the hollow ratio of the test piece is changed by adjusting the diameter of the inner steel pipe and the cross-sectional area of the concrete. When the hollow ratio of the test piece is within a reasonable range, the cross-sectional area of the core concrete with the larger hollow ratio is smaller. However, the cross-sectional area of the inner steel pipe is increasing, and the influence of the two on the bearing capacity of the component is partly offsetting each other. Therefore, combined with the previous analysis of the factors affecting the stainless - steel pipe. The effect of force is small.

Fig 3-5: The effect of hollowness on impact force

3.2.4 Influence of inner pipe diameter-thickness ratio

The variation range of the diameter-to-thickness ratio of the inner tube of the test specimen studied in this paper is 20 ~ 60. In order to investigate the influence of the diameter-to-thickness ratio on the axial compressive performance of stainless - steel tube-concrete and steel tube hollow composite members. Shown are load-displacement curves for specimens with inner tube diameter-thickness ratios of 20, 40, and 60, respectively. It can be seen from the figure that with the increase of the diameter-to-thickness ratio of the test piece, the load. Displacement curve of the component moves slightly downward, and the corresponding ultimate bearing capacities of the test pieces with the diameter-thickness ratio of 20, 40, and 60 are 629KN, 600KN, 580KN. When the diameter-to-thickness ratio of the inner tube increases from 20 to 60, the ultimate bearing capacity of the test piece decreases by 7.7%. Therefore, the diameter-to-thickness ratio of the inner tube affects the axial compressive performance of the stainless - steel tube, concrete and steel tube hollow composite member very small.

Fig 3-6: The effect of different internal pipe

4. Practical calculation methods

Huang Hong^[11] After a large number of experimental studies and parameter analysis, the axial bearing capacity of circular hollow sandwich concrete filled steel tubes was obtained:

$$N_{u1} = N_{osc,u} + N_{i,u}$$

$N_{osc,u}$ Ultimate bearing capacity of outer steel tube and concrete as a whole.

$N_{i,u} = A_{si} f_{yi}$ Is the ultimate bearing capacity of the inner steel tube.

$N_{osc,u}$ Ok

$$N_{osc,u} = f_{scy} A_{sco}$$

$A_{sco} = A_{sc} + A_c$ A_{sc} and A_c Sectional area of outer steel tube and concrete.

Circular hollow sandwich concrete filled steel tube:

$$f_{scy} = C_1 x^2 f_{yo} + C_2 (1.14 + 1.02\xi) f_{ck}$$

$C_1 = \alpha / (1 + \alpha)$, $C_2 = (1 + \alpha_n) / (1 + \alpha)$, α and α_n are steel content rate and nominal steel content rate. According to the development status of stainless - steel pipe concrete described in Chapter 1 of this paper. It can be known that the bearing capacity of stainless - steel pipe concrete is related to the bearing capacity of concrete filled steel pipes. Therefore, this paper considers that the ultimate axial bearing capacity of stainless - steel tube-concrete-steel tube hollow composite members is closely related to the circular hollow sandwich steel tube concrete in which both the inner and outer steel tubes are carbon steel, so it is assumed that:

$$N_u = RN_{u1}$$

Among them, R is the adjustment coefficient of the axial compression bearing capacity after the outer steel pipe is made of stainless steel.

Through parameter analysis, the main factor affecting the ultimate bearing capacity of stainless - steel tube-concrete-steel tube hollow composite members is the nominal steel content ratio, and the constraint effect coefficient is a parameter related to the nominal steel content ratio. It also considers the concrete strength and external Yield strength of steel pipes. This paper uses regression to obtain the relationship between the coefficient R and the constraint effect coefficient. See the equation:

$$R = -0.1608\zeta^2 + 0.5165\zeta + 1.0719$$

5. Conclusion

This paper takes stainless steel pipe-concrete-steel pipe short stubs as research objects. Through finite element simulation, and parameter analysis explained systematically. The mechanical properties of the test specimens under axial compressive load, and based on parameter analysis, a new formula for calculating the axial compressive force of a new type of hollow sandwich concrete composite short column is proposed. The comparison of simulation and test results validates the validity and correctness of the material constitutive, contact properties, and boundary constraints used in the model. Using the orthogonal test principle, based on the verified finite element simulation, the range analysis method was used to analyze the nominal steel content ratio (0.05 -- 0.11), hollow ratio (0.4 ~ 0.8), and concrete strength. (C30 ~ C70), inner tube diameter-thickness ratio (20 ~ 60) most significant. Quantitative parameter analysis of various factors affecting the axial compressive performance of the test piece. Based on this, the axial bearing capacity of stainless - steel tube-concrete-steel tube combination short was proposed practical calculation formula.

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Mohammad Rakibul Hassan
Structural Engineering
Department of Civil Engineering
Taiyuan University of Technology, Shanxi, Taiyuan, PR China
Email: 1801228730@qq.com, rony77717@hotmail.com

Miao Zhai
Structural Engineering
Department of Civil Engineering
Taiyuan University of Technology, Shanxi, Taiyuan, PR China
zhaimiao1997@163.com

Acknowledgments

All praises and thanks be to God Almighty. Taiyuan University of Technology Research Fund Committee (TYUT) for the Research Grant, and to the supervisor for her guidance and recommendations.

Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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